

identical, to ragged stunt disease reported in the Philippines.

In experiments, ragged stunt reduced the yield of Pelita I/1 by 43%. Total yield losses were common in severe cases.

Infection has been as high as 76% in varieties and lines growing under natural

conditions. Rice varieties that showed susceptible reactions include Pelita I/1, Pelita I/2, C4-63, IR5, and IR8. Three promising lines – B2850bSi2-1, B2850bSi2-2, and B2850bSi2-3 – from the breeding department, LP-3 Sukamandi, have apparent resistance.

They are F₄ lines from the cross of B541 b-Kn-91-3/IR2011-15-4-1-2.

Studies are under way to establish etiology, epidemiology, distribution, control, and other factors related to the disease. ❧

Rice ragged stunt disease

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In January 1977, a rice malady was reported in North Cotabato, Mindanao, Philippines, by Mr. Tirona, plant protection officer, Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI). Scientists from BPI and the University of the Philippines at Los Baños observed the disease. In February, the disease was observed at IRRI, particularly in the hybridization block. Scattered diseased plants were later observed in various rice fields in the Philippines. In May, the disease was reported in Indonesia. It seems to be widely distributed in these two countries.

The disease may have long been present at a low level in rice fields, but may have gone unnoticed because the symptoms are not obvious at certain growth stages of the rice plant. In severe cases, more than 90% of rice hills in a field are diseased, and total yield loss results.

The predominant symptoms of the disease are stunting to various degrees at all growth stages (Fig. 1) and ragged, tattered, torn, or serrated leaves (Fig. 2). The disease has been called “ragged stunt,” “infectious gall,” and “Kerdil hampa.”

The diseased plants do not deviate markedly from healthy ones in color and tillering, but are stunted. Other symptoms vary according to the stage of plant growth. At early growth, the predominant symptom is ragged leaves, which gradually become fewer as the plants grow older. Another symptom is vein-swelling or galls (Fig. 3), the result of a proliferation of phloem cells (Fig. 4). The vein-swellings are about 1 mm or less wide and from about 1 mm to more than 1.0 cm long. They are pale yellow in

1. Healthy plant (left) and stunted plant (right) infected with ragged stunt disease.

2. Note the ragged leaves, a symptom of the disease.

color or, less frequently, brown. The vein-swelling often appears on the upper portion of the outer surface of the leaf sheath, particularly adjacent to the collar, and less often on the lower surface of leaf blades. Diseased plants often flower late. Flag leaves are small and

3. Vein-swelling on leaves, a symptom of the disease.

4. The cause of vein-swelling – a proliferation of phloem cells.

often twisted, malformed, or ragged (Fig. 5). Panicle emergence is often incomplete (Fig. 5), but tillers may produce more panicles, often at the upper nodes (Fig. 6). The panicles bear mostly empty grains. The diseased plants can survive for a long time after flowering – more than 6 months in the IRRI greenhouse.

Ragged stunt disease is systemic. When a diseased plant is ratooned, vein-swelling is the only symptom that can

5. Distortion of flag leaves and incomplete emergence of panicles are symptoms of ragged stunt disease.

6. Excessive panicles of infected plants at later growth stages are another symptom of ragged stunt.

be observed in the early regenerated growth; other symptoms appear at booting stage.

So far, studies of ragged stunt transmission through seeds and soil and by mechanical means have yielded no positive results, but the disease can be transmitted by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. The causal agent-vector interaction will probably be categorized in the persistent group. Although biotypes 1, 2, and 3 of the brown planthopper differ in their ability to attack rice varieties, no significant difference has been found in their ability to transmit ragged stunt.

The nature of the causal agent of the ragged stunt disease remains obscure. However, it is not a fungus, bacterium, nematode, or mite. It is probably a virus.

Under natural infection, the following varieties and lines of *O. sativa* were susceptible to ragged stunt: BG34-8, BG90-2, BG374-2, BKN6986-108-2, Gow Ruang 88, IR8, IR20, IR22, IR24, IR26, IR29, IR30, IR3839-1, IR4427-115-3-3-3-3, IR4547-16-3-7, IR4568-586-2-2, IR4625-169-3-3-3, IR4723-345-1-3-1, IR4744-32-1-3-3, KN-IB-461-8-6-9-2, Pelita I/1, and TN1. *O. latifolia* can also be infected.

Since the infection has been noted in rice seedbeds, protecting seedlings and plants during early growth would probably reduce the disease incidence.

Study indicates viral nature of rice ragged stunt disease

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Dip preparations and ultrathin sections of plants naturally infected with ragged stunt disease at the IRRI farm and artificially inoculated by viruliferous *Nilaparvata lugens* were studied with an electron microscope at Hokkaido University. Electron micrographs showed

Electron micrographs show virus particles in dip preparation (top) and in a phloem cell of an ultrathin section (bottom) of a rice plant infected with ragged stunt disease.

polyhedral particles of 50–70 nm. The particles appeared abundantly in phloem cells (see photo), and in cells of the vein-swollings, or galls.

Although the determination of the infectivity of the particles is still under way, the electron micrographs serve as additional evidence that the causal agent of rice ragged stunt disease is a virus.

Resistance to bacterial leaf streak in India

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Bacterial leaf streak, caused by *Xanthomonas translucens*, is sometimes widespread and damaging, causing losses comparable with those from bacterial blight; however, little has been done on the development of resistant varieties. Varieties have been screened by artificial inoculation under natural conditions at Pantnagar since 1973. These results are from kharif 1973 and 1975, when disease pressure was heavy.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in a puddled field with four checks: IR22 (resistant), Krisna (moderately resistant), IR8 (susceptible), and Cauvery (highly susceptible). The entries were inoculated at 45 days after sowing by rubbing bacterial suspension in cotton wool on the undersurface of the leaves. A spray inoculation increased disease pressure. Observations were recorded at the maximum-tillering stage and at 14 days after flowering on a scale of 1–9 (see table).

The following entries were recorded as resistant or moderately resistant to bacterial leaf streak:

KHARIF 1973

Resistant – SMI-6, RP 633, RP 189-2, OR 10-58, and OR 10-237.

Moderately resistant – IR579-119-2-3, CR 10R-157, ARC 5983, entries no. 6328, 6333, 6334, 6335, and 6336, RP 291-20, and RP4-13.

KHARIF 1975

Resistant – AD 1140, Hoyaku/Kolumba 540-1, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-5, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-6, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-7, Shiranui/Goinchiew 35-4, FH 487, MR 249, RP 1017-334-3-6,